

TOMRES: Screening Of Traditional Tomato Varieties For Water Use Efficiency And Nutrient Use Efficiency

Alessandra Ruggiero¹, Giorgia Batelli², Michael James Van Oosten¹, Antonello Costa²,
Stefania Grillo², Albino Maggio¹

¹ Department of Agricultural Sciences, University of Naples Federico II, Portici (NA), Italy

² IBBR CNR, Portici (NA), Italy

Introduction

Traditional varieties of tomato from the Mediterranean region represent a pool of biodiversity that can be mined for novel traits that can be used for the genetic improvement of commercial tomato varieties. As urban development and climate change exacerbate competition for water and critical resources, it is essential commercial production of vegetables increases the Water Use Efficiency (WUE) and Nutrient/Nitrate Use Efficiency (NUE) in order to reduce the environmental impacts in terms of water and fertilizer (Hirel et al., 2007; Erisman et al., 2008). In order to address the anticipated need for improvement of existing commercial varieties (Ruggiero et al., 2017), we are screening over 40 traditional tomato varieties for their WUE, NUE and combined stress indexes to identify genotypes that are particularly efficient in their use of water, nitrogen, or both critical resources. The best performing genotypes will be further evaluated at the molecular and genetic level to determine which traits and genes are responsible for increased WUE and NUE.

Materials and Methods

Each genotype is first evaluated at early stages of development (seedling) *in vitro* for early responses to Low Nutrients (1/10 dose of Nitrogen and Phosphorous) and under osmotic stress (mannitol 200 mM). Growth in terms of FW, leaf area, root length, root area, and root branching were evaluated under Control conditions, Low Nutrient conditions, 200 mM Mannitol, and a combined stress treatment (Low nutrients and mannitol).

Each genotype is then evaluated in a large-scale pot experiment. Ten replicates of ten genotypes are evaluated at each time using 15 L pots filled with sand in a randomized block setup. Each genotype is grown for six weeks under four separate treatments: Control (10.2 mM NO₃⁻), Low Nitrate (2.88 mM NO₃⁻), Drought (50% water) and Combined Stress (2.88 mM NO₃⁻ with 50% water). During the experiment, stomatal conductance, chlorophyll-SPAD, flowering time, and leaf surface temperature are monitored. At harvest (six weeks after transplantation), FW and DW of roots and shoots, leaf number and area, number of internodes, number of lateral branches, height, and root length were measured. Samples from six replicates for each genotype and treatment were snap frozen in liquid nitrogen for further molecular and biochemical analysis. Dry material from six replicates per treatment (roots and shoots) was dried and conserved for ion and total nitrogen content.

Results

Preliminary results from screening of seedlings show that primary root growth is affected by treatments in a genotype specific fashion (Figure 1A). We observed that UNA 04 is reduced in osmotic and combined stresses (Fig. 1B) and UNA 28 is only reduced in osmotic stress (Fig. 1C). The behavior of the two varieties is evident also in large-scale pot experiment: plant height (Figure 2A) and leaf area (Figure 2B) are only affected in drought and combined stress.

Conclusions

Our preliminary results indicate that of the initial 10 genotypes tested, there exists significant variation between the responses to Low Nitrogen, Drought Combined Stresses. We are currently evaluating a second round of 10 genotypes in a second pot experiment. Once all 40 selected genotypes have been

evaluated in pots over the first eight weeks of growth, a second experiment with the best and worst performing genotypes will be conducted for the fully life cycle of the plants.

References

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growth measured as percentage of initial length of varieties.

Figure 2 Plant height (A) and Leaf Area (B) of tomato plants grown in pots filled with sand.